

TECHNIQUES FOR SUSPENDED SEDIMENT MEASUREMENT- A REVIEW

P. B. Khaire^{1*}, V. N. Barai², S. B. Nandgude³, A. A. Atre², A. G. Durgude⁴ and M. S. Patwardhan⁵¹ Ph.D. Research Scholar of Department of Soil and Water Conservation Engineering, Dr. ASCAET, MPKV, Rahuri² Professor of Department of Soil and Water Conservation Engineering, Dr. ASCAET, MPKV, Rahuri³ Professor and Head of Department of Soil and Water Conservation Engineering, Dr. ASCAET, MPKV, Rahuri⁴ Analytical Chemist, Micronutrient Research Scheme, Department of Soil Science & Agricultural Chemistry, MPKV, Rahuri⁵ Professor of Department of Renewable Energy Engineering, Dr. ASCAET, MPKV, Rahuri

*pkhaire348@gmail.com

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Abstract:

Suspended sediment concentration (SSC) plays a crucial role in evaluating hydraulic, environmental, and geomorphological processes, including scouring, deposition, and water quality management. Traditional methods for SSC measurement, such as manual and automatic samplers, provide reliable point data but lack the temporal and spatial resolution required for modern applications. Advances in sediment-surrogate technologies, including optical, acoustic, laser-based, and pressure-difference methods, offer continuous monitoring capabilities with varying levels of accuracy and cost-effectiveness. This paper reviews the principles, operational methodologies, advantages, and limitations of both traditional and surrogate SSC measurement techniques. Optical turbidimeters are cost-effective but require site-specific calibration and are prone to saturation. Acoustic technologies excel in high SSC environments but face challenges with sediment size ambiguity. Laser diffraction instruments provide detailed particle size distribution but are limited by signal saturation and maintenance needs. Pressure-difference systems demonstrate robustness for high SSC measurements but lack commercial availability and consistency in low SSC conditions. Each method's applicability depends on site characteristics, sediment properties, and monitoring objectives. This review highlights the need for integrated approaches combining traditional and advanced technologies to achieve accurate and comprehensive SSC assessments.

Keywords: Suspended sediment concentration (SSC), Surrogate methods, Environmental monitoring, Optical methods, Pressure-difference techniques

Introduction

The measurement of suspended sediment concentration (SSC) and the analysis of its distribution are necessary to solve many hydraulic problems. The concentration of suspended sediment is necessary to assess morphological changes, including reservoir deposition (Tao 2008, Hainly et al 1995), coastal erosion (Archetti and Romagnoli 2011, Archetti and Zanuttigh 2010, Carniel et al 2011, Domeneghetti et al 2014), scouring or deposition around hydraulic structures (Wang et al 2015), and deposition in navigation channels (Guerrero et al 2013, Paarlberg et al 2015). Given that the suspended sediments in water have an impact on water quality (Bilotta and Brazier 1981), habitat preservation (Ceola et al., 2013), irrigation water supply (Guerrero, 2014), and water diversion engineering (Pathak et al., 2004) would also be closely related to the amount of suspended sediment in water. In addition, SSC is a very important parameter for channel design, as it affects flow resistance (Yu and Lim 2003). Therefore, SSC measurement is very important in environmental and hydraulic engineering studies and practices.

There are several methods for measuring suspended sediment concentration (SSC) in water bodies. Traditional methods include gravimetric analysis using various types of samples such as hand-held solid bottle samplers, handheld and handline, cable and reel samplers, bag samplers, differential pressure, deep-integrated suspended sediment samplers, automatic samplers, etc. Traditional grab sample measurements lack the spatial or temporal perspective of water quality required for effective water resource assessment and management. In recent decades, technological advances in electronics and computing have led to new devices that produce accurate SSC measurements in water. Recently, new alternative technologies are being used for continuous monitoring of suspended sediment concentrations. Sediment surrogate technologies are defined as instruments accompanied by operational and analytical methodologies that allow the acquisition of temporally and/or spatially dense river sediment datasets without the need for routine collection and analysis of physical samples except for calibration purposes. They are capable of providing a continuous and dense time series of data that will be empirically converted to the units of interest.

Many such measurement techniques are available for the assessment of suspended sediment that can be used with varying degrees of success. In view of the above, the article provides a detailed description of the different methods available for the estimation of suspended

sediment. Techniques are described, including their operating principles, advantages and disadvantages.

Traditional techniques for measuring suspended sediment Samplers and sampling methods

The purpose of a suspended sediment sampler is to obtain a representative sample of the water-sediment mixture moving in the water flow near the sampler's water intake. There are two categories of traditional suspended sediment samplers: manual samplers and automatic samplers. Manual sampling includes both instantaneous and isokinetic sampling. Manual sampling is applicable to sampling streams that do not meet any of the following criteria for isokinetic sampling: sampling depth greater than approximately 0.3 m and (or) average velocity greater than approximately 0.5 m/s. Isokinetic samplers - those that collect a stream of river water without changing the speed or direction of flow - include those with rigid sample bottles (bottle samplers) and soft bag samplers (bag samplers).

Rigid Bottle Samplers

When a suspended this sediment sampler is immersed with the mouth pointing directly into the flow within the sampler's calibrated velocity range, a portion of the flow enters the sample container through the orifice and the air in the container escapes due to the combined effect of three forces: 1. A positive dynamic head at the orifice inlet due to flow. 2. A negative head at the air tube outlet due to flow separation. 3. Positive pressure due to the height difference between the inlet of the mouth and the outlet of the air discharge tube. Under these conditions, a calibrated isokinetic sampler will collect a sample with a suspended sediment concentration (SSC) and particle size diameter (PSD) essentially unchanged from those at the sampling point in the stream and will result in a representative sample.

Handheld and handline samplers

Depth Integrator Sampler The USD-49 is an integrated depth sampler. The sample is lowered at a uniform rate from the water surface to the stream bed, immediately lowered, and then raised to the water surface. The sampler continues to sample for the duration of the dive. At least one sample should be taken at each selected vertical in the cross section of the watercourse. A clean bottle is used for each sample. The USD-49 sampler has a contoured cast brass body in which a round or square bottle sample container is enclosed. The sampler head is hinged to allow access to the sample container. US Depth Integrator, Portable (DH)-81, US DH-48, US DH-59, US DH-76 and US DH-95: Where watercourses are fordable or accessible by canal, short distance bridge, cableway or boat, and one of the six lightweight samplers can be used

to sample suspended sediment via a cotton swab or hand line. The US DH-81 Sampler, which is mounted on a jump rod, consists of a US DH-81A adapter and a US D-77 cap and nozzle. All parts can be autoclaved, allowing a deep integrated sample to be collected for weighted and unbiased bacterial analysis. Any standard single-threaded mason jar bottle can be used with the US DH-81 sampler. The no-sampling zone - the distance between the centerline of the mouth and the flow bed when the sampler contacts a flat bed - varies depending on the size of the bottle used. The US DH-81 is advantageous for sampling in sub-zero temperatures because the plastic sampling head and nozzle attach directly to plastic or glass bottles. Sampler bodies constructed of metal are relatively efficient at removing heat from the nozzle, exhaust air, and bottle, increasing the risk of ice blockage and/or discharge port and, therefore, potentially negating the isokinetic sampling properties.

Cable and reel samplers

These types of samplers can be used to sample suspended sediment in impassable streams less than 15 feet (4.6 m) deep. The USP-61 suspended load sampler consists of a simple bronze casting (= 50 kg), which includes a small bottle (= 500 ml). The sampler head is curved to allow access to the bottle. The inlet, which can be opened or closed by means of an electric valve, directs it directly into the incoming stream.

Bag Samplers

As With solid isokinetic bottle samplers, water enters the bag sampler through a mouth. However, the bag sampler does not have a discharge port and the sample container is a collapsible bag. Air is manually removed from the bag before immersing the sampler. The empirically determined minimum transit rate for a bag sampler is limited by the inlet mouth/nozzle and the volume of the bag; and the maximum transit velocity is 0.4 times the average vertical flow velocity. When using a Teflon bag, these are bag samplers capable of collecting unbiased samples for trace element analysis, except for those collected for suspended sediment analysis.

Automatic samplers

Automatic samplers are useful for collecting suspended sediment samples during periods of rapid changes in water flow due to stormwater runoff and to reduce the need for manual measurements associated with intensive programs (Federal Interagency Sedimentation Project, 1981). However, in some circumstances the use of samplers Automated data collection methods can be more costly than an observer (Johnson, 1997) at the same location. Automatic samplers, and particularly pump samplers, often require more frequent site visits by field personnel than would be necessary at a conventional monitoring station due to their mechanical complexity, power requirements, and limited sampling capacity. The use of automatic sampling does not obviate the need for medium- and high-throughput cross-sampling. Furthermore, the use of autosamplers generally results in a decrease in data quality because samples are rarely, if ever, collected isokinetically. This conclusion is particularly true for automated sampling in streams carrying high percentages of suspended sand material. The most commonly used automatic samplers are autopump samplers, which require power to take water samples. Single-stage samplers, which rely on changes in level and (or) flow

rates to passively collect water and sediment samples during the rising phase of a hydrograph, are also available.

Surrogate Suspended Sediment Measurement Techniques

Advances in surrogate suspended sediment techniques for river transport monitoring programs show varying degrees of promise to supplement and/or replace traditional data collection methods based on routine physical laboratory sampling and subsurface analysis. Research-based and commercially available technologies that operate on turbidity (transmissometry and nephelometry), laser and digital optics, pressure variation, and acoustic principles have been or remain the focus of field and laboratory testing by USGS and other organizations. The benefits and limitations associated with each suspended sediment surrogate technology should be considered in the design of the monitoring program network to select the most appropriate technology. General considerations should include physical location, flow, sediment characteristics, and monitoring objectives. Examples of specific factors that may limit or enhance the effectiveness of an alternative technology: cost (purchase, installation, operation and data analysis), reliability, robustness, accuracy, measurement volume, sensitivity to biological fouling, volumetric versus SSC mass determinations and adaptability in the range of SSC mass and PSD in the flow.

Turbidity-based techniques

Principle: A light beam passes through a small sample volume in the case of continuous measurement technique instruments based on optical technology (CMT). These instruments (also called turbidimeters) measure the scattered or transmitted light, which is used to calculate the turbidity in the sample volume. Turbidity is an expression of the optical properties of a sample that causes light rays to be scattered and absorbed instead of being transmitted in a straight line through the sample (Ziegler, 2003; Anderson, 2005).

Light scattering based turbidimeter: Figure 1 shows a turbidity measurement with the scattered light detector position, which estimates the SSC value. The most coherent light scattering angle is 90° relative to the source radius [Bin et al. , 2009; Merten et al. , 2013], which is used in nephelometry. The expression for the intensity of scattered light is as follows (Sutherland et al., 2000):

$$F = 1.5 \times V \times C \times E \times Q_s / (\rho \times D)$$

where F is the flux scattered by the suspended particles, E is the irradiance of the light source, V is the scattering volume, C is the SSC, D is the particle diameter, ρ is the particle density, and Q_s is the diffusion efficiency. The intensity of the scattered light is proportional to the SSC if other variables remain constant. In the equation, the distribution volume (V) and the amount of radiated signal (E) are instrument-specific constants that depend on the type of instrument. The distributed luminous flux (F), which gives the SSC value, depends on site-specific parameters ρ , Q_s , and D. This dependence requires proper calibration of scattering-based turbidimeters to site conditions. In light scattering sensors, the scattering amplitude depends on the surface area of the particle concentration, as suggested by the common intuition that objects reflect light in proportion to their surface area rather than their volume. This is why scattering sensors must change calibration for different particle sizes.

Fig. 1 Turbidity measurement at different angles

Turbidimeter based on light transmission: The Lambert-Beer law is strictly applicable to transmission sensors, which collect information on the intensity of light transmission in water as follows [Ochiai S. and K. Kashiwaya, 2010].

$$I = I_0 \times e^{-k \times c \times l}$$

where I is the transmitted light intensity, I_0 is the incident light intensity, c is the sediment concentration, l is the optical path length, and k is a constant. A known value of the constant k allows the SSC to be calculated from the measurement of the transmitted intensity. The performance of turbidimeters depends on the amount of signal received. As the SSC value increases, the transmitted signal decreases, but the backscattered signal increases.

Turbidity instruments have no moving parts (unless they are equipped with optical wipers) and can be deployed in situ and provide rapid sampling capability. Site-specific empirical calibrations are necessary to convert measurements into reliable cross-sectional SSC estimates.

Availability and Applications

Turbidimeters are readily available instruments and are the best among all other techniques. Turbidimeters are used for continuous SSC measurement under wide-field conditions in rivers, oceans and hydroelectric power plants. Haimann et al. (2014) used turbidity to determine SSC, sediment transport and sediment loading on the Hainburg Danube road bridge. The specific calibration of the instrument in their study was performed with a standard formazin turbidity solution. They adopted two methods for in-situ calibration, such as a correction factor for each sample collection and a simple linear regression using multiple sample collections (73 samples over a 2-year period for calibration). Studies have shown that site-specific calibration is essential for continuous turbidity measurement techniques (CMT). In their study, Navratil et al. [2011] revealed uncertainties in the use of turbidimeters for field monitoring of SSC and sediment load in a small river. They found uncertainty in SSC measurements of up to 70% in some cases, while uncertainty in sediment yield was in the range of 20–50%. OBS probes have been used successfully for high SSC values up to 40 g/l (Gentile et al., 2010), however, the results were found to be significantly dependent on the sand fraction content of the sediments. Downing J. (2006) found that the sensitivity of OBS with identical electron counts varied by a factor of 200 for sediments ranging in size from about 1 to 500 μm . Felix et al. (2012) found that the transmissometer provided SSC up to 20 g/l in hydroelectric applications.

The optical approach has a number of limitations, including the following:

Turbidity time series data at a given point may not be representative of sediment conditions in the river section.

Saturation of the turbidimeter signal can occur, resulting in erroneous (constant) values for all SSC values exceeding a maximum value.

Biofouling or damage to the optical windows may require frequent field visits for instrument servicing.

The response of the instrument to grain size, composition, color, shape and coating can be variable and, therefore, can reduce the accuracy of SSC values obtained without additional calibration.

Acoustic surrogates

Principle: In instruments based on acoustic technology, a piezoelectric transducer sends a sound pulse into the environment. The particles in the medium return some of the energy of the pulse. This dissipated energy is usually picked up by the transducer itself, which now acts as a receiver. The strength of the received echo is a measure of sediment concentration (Thorne and Hurther, 2014), somewhat like radar operation. The fundamental complexity of acoustic backscattering (although separate from radar) is that the strength of the returned echo is determined by two parameters: the size of the target particles and the concentration of the target particles. Thus, two unknowns determine one measured parameter - the echo power, and therefore this problem cannot be solved. Therefore, multi-frequency systems have been built.

Based on the return time of the scattered acoustic signal, the instrument measures discrete layers of water within the sample volume. Acoustic backscattering remains an attractive and only partially proven technology for sediment measurements. The cost of a single-frequency acoustic CMT instrument is slightly higher than that of a fully equipped turbidimeter. Since biofouling has little effect on the acoustic sensors, their maintenance costs are lower than those of turbidimeters. However, there is the potential for higher overall cost due to the difficulty associated with signal inversion and calibration of acoustic instruments.

Limitations:

As with turbidimeters, acoustic measurements from single-frequency systems can vary due to changes in sediment concentration or size, creating size-concentration ambiguities.

Acoustic measurements are sensitive to the ratio of sediment size to acoustic wavelength, and a somewhat narrow frequency range is optimal for PSD estimation with multi-frequency acoustics.

The sensitivity of acoustic surrogates for suspended sediment is limited at low concentrations and may not generally be applicable for concentrations below approximately 10 mg/l for frequencies in the 0.5 to 5 MHz frequency range.

CMT based on laser diffraction

Principle: Laser diffraction instruments exploit the principles of small-angle forward scattering to derive volume PSDs. At small forward scattering angles, laser diffraction from spherical particles is essentially identical to diffraction from an aperture of equal size (Agrawal and Pottsmith, 1994). Thus, this method of determining PSDs (and, by inference, volumetric SSC values) is generally insensitive to changes in particle color or composition, although deviation from sphericity produces a bias in the calculated PSD compared to that of the sieve. For example, Agrawal et al. (2008) showed that natural particles measured by laser diffraction are expected to be approximately 20–40% larger than sieved spheres of known sizes. They describe a new method that allows the calculation of PSDs of equivalent sizes.

Availability and Applications

Currently, an in situ version of this type of instrument is commercially available from only one manufacturer (Sequoia Scientific, Inc., 2012). First used in the early 1990s (Agrawal and Pottsmith, 1994), the current version of a laser diffraction instrument that can be deployed unattended to provide time series of PSD volumes and SSC values is the laser in situ scattering and transmissometry (LISST)-100X. The LISST instruments use a 32-ring detector to detect light scattered by particles illuminated by a laser beam at small forward angles. This data was inverted to determine PSDs at 32 size classes between 1.25-250 and 2.5-500 μm (limits that are not fundamental and may be extended in the future). The standard sample path of this device is a cylindrical volume with a diameter of about 6 mm and a length of 50 mm (essentially a point measurement).

Laser sensors are being investigated as an alternative monitoring protocol for monitoring the distribution of suspended sediment at a USGS stream gauge on the Colorado River near the Grand Canyon, Arizona, USA, located 164 km downstream of Glen Canyon Dam (Topping et al. , 2004). A canyon-walled LISST-100B provides continuous sediment transport data (SSC and PSD in the range of 0.0012 to 0.25 mm) that can reduce the uncertainty in sediment transport estimates. Filippa etc. (2011) found high measurement accuracy in a river and estuarine environment with LISST using different path lengths, but they also observed that the instrument underestimated particle sizes larger than 20 μm and overestimated particles smaller than 20 μm .

Limitations

In situ laser measurements cannot be representative of the sediment conditions in the river section.

Saturation of the laser optical signal can occur at an SSC level about half that at which a standard in situ turbidimeter saturates.

As with turbidimeters, frequent field visits may be necessary to clean the optics if antifouling caps are not used.

Differential Pressure Technique

Principle: CMT based on pressure change consists of two highly sensitive pressure sensors located at different fixed heights in a water column. These sensors continuously monitor the density of the liquid. The difference in the density value obtained gives the SSC value after correction for the water temperature. If the water contains suspended sediment, the pressure difference between the upper and lower sensors is higher than in clear water conditions. Knowing the density of pure water and particles, these pressure differences are converted to SSC under quasi-steady conditions. The pressure difference technique uses the difference in measured fluid density in the following equation to calculate SSC:

$$SSC = K(\delta p / (\delta h \times g)) - K \times \rho_w$$

$$K = \rho_s / (\rho_s - \rho_w)$$

where δp is the pressure difference between the two points, δh is the height difference between the two points, SSC is the suspended sediment concentration, in kg/m^3 , ρ_w is the density of clear water in kg/m^3 , ρ_s is the density of dry sediment in kg/m^3 and g is the acceleration due to gravity in m/s^2 . The K value is obtained by in situ calibration and by continuously measuring an auxiliary parameter, temperature.

Availability and Applications

The availability of a commercial differential pressure instrument is still a problem, although essential parts, such as accurate pressure sensors, are readily available. The cost of a differential pressure instrument is slightly higher than that of a turbidimeter (Gray J. R. and J.W. Gartner, 2010). Due to inconsistent results, the pressure change instrument is no longer manufactured (Gray J. R. and J. W. Gartner, 2009) and other tests of a pressure change instrument have been suspended by the USGS (Gray J. R. and J. W. Gartner, 2010). However, Hsu and Cai (2010) have shown that the pressure difference technique is able to provide consistent results in the Ji-Ji flume, possibly due to the high SSC value at the flume site. Lewis and Rasmussen [1999] conducted a study to calculate SSC in controlled laboratory conditions using pressure difference technology. A result with an accuracy of 3% (543 ± 14 mg/l) was obtained when determining the SSC of glass microspheres. Hsu and Cai (2010) applied pressure difference measurement to field applications. They found that SSC measurement using the pressure variation technique is more accurate at higher SSC and greater distance between the two pressure sensors.

Advantages and Disadvantages

The advantages of pressure difference-based CMT are as follows:

- The distinctive advantage of differential pressure technology is the ability to measure SSC above 10 g/l.
- Pressure difference-based CMT is relatively robust and does not present problems of biofouling or signal drift (Gray J. R. and J.W. Gartner, 2009).
- CMT based on pressure change is less expensive.

This measurement method has several limitations, as follows:

- The assumption of the technology calculation principle, that the SSC in the vertical profile on the low pressure sensor is constant, cannot be true.
- The differential pressure technology depends on the sensitivity of the pressure transducers, the turbulence of the flow, the concentration of dissolved solids, the variation of the water density and the density of suspended solids.
- Due to the low signal-to-noise ratio at low SSC, this technology is not reliable at SSC below 10 g/l (Gray J. R. and J. W. Gartner, 2010).

In a CMT based on pressure difference consisting of two sensors, burying the lower sensor or not burying the upper sensor results in a malfunction of the instrument.

Conclusion

Accurate measurement of suspended sediment concentration (SSC) is essential for effective hydraulic and environmental engineering practices, including sediment transport analysis, water quality management, and habitat preservation. Traditional techniques, while reliable, are labor-intensive and lack the spatial and temporal granularity required for modern assessments. Emerging sediment-surrogate technologies, such as optical, acoustic, laser, and pressure-difference methods, address these limitations by enabling continuous monitoring with automated systems.

Among these, turbidity-based sensors offer cost-effective solutions for low SSC environments but require extensive calibration and maintenance. Acoustic methods are better suited for high SSC applications but struggle with sediment size-concentration ambiguities. Laser diffraction systems provide detailed particle size distribution data but are hindered by signal saturation and maintenance needs. Pressure-difference techniques are robust for high SSC conditions but lack widespread adoption due to inconsistent results at low SSC levels.

The review underscores the importance of selecting measurement techniques based on site-specific conditions, sediment properties, and project objectives. Combining traditional methods with advanced technologies can enhance accuracy and address limitations inherent in standalone approaches. Future research should focus on developing hybrid systems that integrate multiple techniques and leverage advancements in sensor technology, data analytics, and automation to improve SSC monitoring's precision and reliability across diverse environments.

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